

Systems

Interoperability

LMS Integration

Experimentation
Environment

Virtual
environment

Physical testing
classroom

Standardization
& Architecture

Available
documentation

API MVP

Security / Privacy

Privacy standards

Data management

EdTech Inventory

Available inventory
of applications

Integration with other
resources

Strategy

Vision

Vision alignment with EdTech

Changes to overcome

Does your institution consider EdTech anywhere in its vision or mission plans?

Does your institution consider EdTech as an answer for obstacles it currently faces now?

Steering

Active steering of EdTech strategy

Expectation management

Is your institution attempting to steer or guide EdTech innovations?

Is there an overview for understanding the expectations of what EdTech does or will do in the near future of your institution?

Budget

Incentivizing EdTech

Reimbursement for experimentation

What incentives are there for experimenting with or adopting EdTech in your institution?

Are there reimbursement packages for experimenters of EdTech?

Decision making

Successful experimentation

Taking on new EdTech

When is it decided and by who when an experiment is successful?

Who are the stakeholders that make decisions about the finalization of new EdTech in your institution?

Responsibility

Ownership

Board has stake

Roadmap

What stake does a board or strategy team have in the successful implementation of EdTech?

Has a roadmap been drawn for understanding the future role of strategists in EdTech?

Structure

Processes

Experiment protocols

Adoption, application processes

Innovation processes

There are agreed on protocols of how to safely experiment with EdTech tools in the classroom

There are clear guidelines how of to adopt a new EdTech tool into the institution

Procurement

Exit strategy

Innovative procurement

Sustainable development

There are guidelines outlining how older or unused EdTech tools will be removed from the institution

Is your institution considering innovating their procurement strategy?

Agility

Change management

AGILE processes

Are AGILE processes being embedded in your institutions workflows?

People

Culture

Safe space to fall

Innovation(?)

Culture of experimentation

Does your organization allow for and encourage space for failure in workshops and experimentation?

Is innovation part of the culture in your institution?

Are there mentors or leaders cultivating experimentation in EdTech processes within your organization?

Behavior

Community

Center for learning and education

EdTech community development

External relations

Shared values

Community of practice

Has your institution developed a center for learning and education?

Is there a group of individuals who have stake in forming an EdTech community?

Are vendors or external organizations invited to develop their technologies within your institution?

Is there a shared consensus of what values EdTech brings to your institution?

Your community of EdTech experiments primarily, research and discussion come second

Competencies

Digital literacy

Change capacity

Pedagogical changes

Job description

There are courses that enhance the digital skills for education professionals

Staff are capable of changing tools or ways of teaching with new tools

Staff are capable of recognizing how EdTech tool(s) adds value to their educational work

Leadership

Ownership

Mission alignment

EdTech strategy

Leadership takes on ownership for university strategists in applying EdTech strategy

It's clear that EdTech tools are aligned to the mission statement of the university

There is a strategy document that acknowledges the importance of EdTech within the institution